

NOVASOIL

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

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Report on first round of multiplier event

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Contributors	ALL

QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCEDURES

This document has been reviewed by the NOVASOIL consortium according to the national reports and comments received

TABLE REVISION HISTORY DELIVERABLE

Row	Version	Date	Reviewers	Description
1	V1.0	24/02/2023	EVENOR	Draft version circulated by email
2	V1.1	27/02/2023	ULEEDS, ZSA and METK	Version updated based on inputs received
3	V2.0	28/02/2023	WU, IDECO, NBU	Final version with minor changes from previous version

Project Consortium

N°	Participant organisation name	Country
1	EVENOR TECH SLU	ES
2	LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG	GE
3	ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA	LV
4	NEW BULGARIAN UNIVERSITY	BU
5	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
6	KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	DK
7	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	GE
8	ASSEMBLEE DES REGIONS EUROPEENNES FRUITIERES LEGUMIERES ET HORTICOLES	FR
9	ISTITUTO DELTA ECOLOGIA APPLICATA SRL	IT
10	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	IT
11	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	NL
12	CENTRE OF ESTONIAN RURAL RESEARCH AND KNOWLEDGE	EE
13	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	ES
14	UNIVERSITA DI PISA	IT
15	ASOCIACION AGRARIA JOVENES AGRICULTORES DE SEVILLA	ES
16	UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	GB

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1 List of Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
ME	Multiplier event
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
CoP	Community of Practice
SDGS30	Sustainable Development Goals 2030
EU	European Union
CS	Case Study
DoA	Description of Action
ES	Ecosystem Services

2 Executive summary

This document reports on activities carried out under task 5.4 (Multiplier events) in the framework of WP5 (Building a Community of Practice and dissemination strategy) of the NOVASOIL project.

This document includes information on the first round of Multiplier Events carried out by partners in the few months of the project in order to attract attention and receive input from participants about the planned activities. In total were 10 MEs held during the first few months of the project.

A second round of Multiplier Events will take place at the end of the project.

3 Introduction

At the beginning of the project, partners have been asked to organize a Multiplier Event in their respective countries.

The purpose of the MEs is to strengthen the links and involvement of stakeholders. In addition to implementing strategies for information flow and co-working, as well supporting successful surveys and questionnaires, and to launch invitations for further participation in project activities.

During the project lifetime, two MEs will be organized by one partner in each country, except France where due to the characteristics of one of the partners the event was transnational. The first round of ME aimed to attract stakeholder's attention to the project, to include them from the beginning.

This document includes a brief summary of the discussion as well as a general overview of what participants thought about the project, and any inputs regarding case studies in their region.

4. Multiplier Events

In total, there were 10 MEs held during the first few months of the project. They were held across Europe, and attracted a range of stakeholders. The first round of events took place between January and February in the form of workshops with invited participants from a range of different backgrounds. This included members of local, national and European policy makers, farmers, industry and NGO as well as prospective case study participants. The workshops were distributed over time in a slightly different way than expected by the project, in order to allow the best possible engagement of stakeholders (given most of them were close to winter holidays 2023).

4.1 Bulgaria

NBU organised two days of multiplier events with a total of 23 representatives participants. WP2 and WP5 were the WPs voted as more interesting for the audience. However, new incentives, soil health business models and the final toolbox were the more interesting project outcomes. However, the CoP was voted on as a relevant outcome highlighting the relevance to build a CoP around soil health business.

Winery sector is relevant in Bulgaria. In fact, there is a problem with unregistered farmers emphasized by a participant. On the other hand, wine tourism could be relevant too considering that the audience looks to introduce some novel business models in this direction from NOVASOIL outcomes.

There is a difference between implementation of eco-schemes in the Bulgaria' regions so new business opportunities may provide new incentives for farmers and soil health improvement.

4.2 Denmark

The event organised by University of Copenhagen involved nine participants from research, public administration and non-profit agricultural research and development association.

Market-based instruments were an interesting topic by the audience regarding carbon farming and carbon credits. Furthermore, they highlighted that there are other ecosystem services which should be focused too.

One recommendation was to develop a matrix-like mapping about positive/negative/no trade-offs between key ESs affected by soil health measures. Another recommendation was to monitor the existing ongoing policy initiatives at different levels (EU and national) related to soil health in order to adapt NOVASOIL outcomes if new policies or initiatives are introduced during project lifetime.

4.3 Estonia

The event organized by METK brought together more than 18 participants (33% belong to public sector, meanwhile 17 % were farmers and other 50% were researchers).

Participants highlighted some concerns about carbon farming due to the lack of information about measurements, regulation and potential or not penalties in negative scenarios. However, there are other qualitative parameters required for soil health. Soil biodiversity should be more emphasized to be measured.

Soil certification is intended to be voluntary but the system must be standardised and regulated and, for that, a participatory process with stakeholders must be implemented to the final design of policy recommendations.

4.4 France

AREFLH organised an online event with 16 participants. To sum up the event, challenge was the word more used due to the relevance of project outcomes and the need to really implement business models to have a positive impact on soil health.

Some clarifications about business models concepts and definitions were provided. Regarding the final NOVASOIL tool-box, participants highlighted the need to involve existing knowledge at local level for particular regions.

The possibility to be part of the Community of Practice around project objectives was very well accepted as well as to collaborate with another initiative on the soil.

4.5 Germany

TUM and ZALF organised an online event with 20 participants including moderators. Innovative was the word used to sum up the project thoughts by the Germany stakeholders. How soil health can be defined including biodiversity and climate certificates as topics related.

Most of the case studies interesting by the audience are related to agricultural business cases about organic farming, society involvement and nature protection.

The participants highlighted that there are several challenges to implement soil health business models: 1) reduce administrative load by farmers; 2) consider external factors in results-oriented or measure-oriented payments; 3) to provide a clear definition of soil health (with parameters); 4) to implement robust and feasible measurement methods; 5) fairness due to the annual fluctuation in hummus; 6) policy improvements to overcome potential barriers for private initiatives and; 7) increase the appreciation by society toward soil health.

4.6 Italy

The ME organised by UNIPI, UNIFE and IDECO brought together about 39 participants from different sectors (NGO, Private sector, Public administration, etc.).

The audience showed a high interest in the next evolutions in terms of soil policies. However, there is a need to coordinate efforts to increase rural actors' willingness to invest in soil health. For that, the proposed toolkit of the NOVASOIL project as possible organisational solutions and their effectiveness and implementability.

Finally, the participants recommended focusing on incentives to facilitate the diffusion of available knowledge and practices.

4.7 Latvia

ZSA organized online meeting with 137 participants, including, moderator and project staff. The majority of the participants were farmers, representing different agriculture sectors' as well as advisors, civil servants and other interested parties.

Healthy soil is the main prerequisite for growing healthy plants. With support of the Novasoil project will be presented the successful business cases to promote the soil health in the toolbox.

The participants admitted the project importance for the sustainable farming practices, therefore showed interest for following the NOVASOIL project activities and interest for participating in the exchange of experience and training activities.

In the meeting was also presented ZSA DIH environment where will be presented project showcase on eco-schemes with soil friendly agricultural practices. The eco-schemes are very actual topic for the society so the project helps for business development and also providing society awareness.

4.8 Netherlands

WU involved 17 participants in the Dutch ME (14 in person and three online). The event featured contributions of EFFECT, CONSOLE, and Contract 2.0.

The NOVASOIL project was perceived positively by the participants. Farmers expressed their need to obtain alternative income models that allow them to benefit from public goods. However, they also highlighted that the current system needs to be changed in order to make these business models successful. Farmers, for instance, expressed their doubts about whether society is willing to pay for public goods.

For the upcoming analyses the participants highlighted that the voluntary nature of participation in carbon farming requires engaged farmers and that the social contexts should be considered. Furthermore, they pointed out that relaxations of current regulations could be an essential legal incentive, as current AES often only offer payments.

Evaluating current contracts for AES flexibility (through frequent renegotiation or result-based schemes) was perceived as an important aspect. Whether flexibility can be granted in contracts for carbon trade / AES could be another point to think about in upcoming analyses.

4.9 Spain

ASAJA-Sevilla, EVENOR and UPM organised the Spanish ME with 25 participants.

They highlighted the alignment of project outcomes with SDGS30 and the EU Soil Mission. Policy innovation and innovative business models were selected as more interesting by the participants.

Finally, some participants proposed potential collaborations involving additional CS to test, monitor and validate ecosystem services provision under different business models. As well as, in order to promote investment in soil health a good communication and dissemination strategy.

4.10 United Kingdom

The University of Leeds' multiplier event engaged nine participants representing stakeholders from the agri-food sector, water services sector, and civil society involved in Landscape Enterprise Networks (LENs) in the UK.

Participants indicated that they were interested to be part of the CoP around soil health and to explore the strengths and weaknesses of the LENs business

model. Participants also expressed an interest in contributing to the development of a toolbox for scaling up soil health business models and policy innovations that will facilitate the stacking of payments and a framework outlining how private sector actors can invest in soil health.

Participants highlighted the importance of taking a multifunctional landscape level perspective on ecosystem services provision and recognising the co-benefits of managing soil health. Finally, participants expressed an interest in continuing the discussion regarding soil health business models beyond the multiplier event.

5. Conclusions

There was a formidable positive consensus regarding the NOVASOIL project made by participants. In many countries there is a huge interest in soil health as well as the toolbox and business models that provide support mechanisms to provide and improve soil health.

The NOVASOIL project offers an opportunity to raise awareness of soil health amongst investors, farmers and landowners as well as to local and national policy makers. Finally, project' outcomes will promote the investment on soil health highlighting additional benefits in terms of economic, society and environment factors.

This will be taken forward by WP5 in communicating and disseminating the work of the project.

According to the DoA, there will be a 2nd report on the second round of multiplier events that will form Deliverable 5.4 due in month 35.

6 Acknowledgment

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7. Multiplier Event Reports

BULGARIA

Workshop agenda

Venue: **meeting room of Hotel Markovo, region Plovdiv, municipality Rhodopes, village of Markovo 4108, locality "Isaka" 44A**

Workshop "Multiplier Event" 16 - 17 February 2023

PROGRAM

Time	Activity
16.02.2023 Thursday	
12:00 – 14:00	Registration
14:00 – 14:15	Opening - <i>Prof. Dimitre Nikolov, PhD, scientific leader of the project</i>
14:15 – 14:45	Presentation of the project, WP1 and WP2 - <i>Prof. Dimitre Nikolov, PhD, scientific leader of the project</i>
14:45 - 15:00	Discussion: main questions about the project
15:00 – 15:30	Coffee break
15:30 – 16:00	Presentation of the project, WP3 and WP4 - <i>Prof. Ivan Boevsky, PhD</i>
16:00 – 16:15	Discussion: main questions about the project
16:15 – 16:30	Presentation of the project, WP5 and WP6 – <i>chief assist. prof. Ekatherina Tzvetanova, PhD</i>
16:30 – 17:00	Discussion: main questions about the project
17.02.2023 Friday	
09:00 – 09:30	Presentation of the research area – <i>Assoc. Prof. Tsvetelina Marinova, PhD</i>
09:30 – 10:00	Presentation of the approach and inventory, and mapping of incentives for improving soil health – <i>chief assist. prof. Krasimir Kostenarov, PhD</i>
10:00 – 10:30	Coffee break
10:30 – 11:30	Discussion: main questions about the project
11:30 – 12:00	Rating and feedback
12:00	Closing the meeting

Introduction

NBU organized the first MPE in person at Hotel Markovo, Marcovo village. A total of 23 representatives took part in the meeting. They have different

agricultural specializations and backgrounds: academic, industrial, farmers, and other sectors.

The multiplier event was focused on showing the main project's objectives, providing an overview of WPs and expected outcomes, and collecting feedback about project perception. Discussion on the interest in case studies and expected results were made.

In terms of the audience, 30% of the participants belong to the private sector, followed by Wineries and Wine growers with 26% and Consulting services with 22%. The public administration (including the Paying agency) and NGOs and research represent 13% and 9%, respectively.

Figure 1. Type of entities distribution

A total of 68 wineries are operating in the Plovdiv region (BG CS) according to the regional Executive agency on vine and wine (EAVW). Some of them (Rumelia, Starosel, Manastira, and the Wine-growing cooperative "Brestovitsa") participated in the NOVASOIL multiplier event in Bulgaria. In terms of size, in Bulgaria is applied the following classification are small wineries which produce below 100 000 litres and large wineries with total production above 100 000 litres. Using this classification, all participants of the first MPE are large.

Project presentation

During the first day of the workshop (16/02/2023) it was presented the project goals and each project's WP. The participants united around the opinion that the project sets significant and important goals, tasks, and

expected results. They are aspiring and in line with global challenges related to sustainable development, environmental protection, and the European Union's Green deal, as well as the Bulgarian soil strategy 20-30 and the new Bulgarian Rural Development Program 23-27. In addition, they are relevant, useful for practice, and adequate for their organizations' future. Therefore, they are particularly interested in the project and would be actively involved with whatever is necessary for its implementation.

At the end of the first day of the MPE, it was organized voting for the CoP members about two questions:

1. Which WP is considered more interesting?
2. Which of the main results are more beneficial?

It was applied the following voting approach:

- before each question, there was a presentation on the topic;
- on the final slide, there was the relevant question and all possible answers, so the participants were able to see the answers all the time;
- all participants vote for a maximum of three answers.

According to the first question answers, *WP2 Analysis and Development of Business Models to Promote Soil Health* and the *WP5 Building a Community of Practice and dissemination strategy* are the most interesting WPs, with 25% of respondents selecting them. *WP4 Envisioning incentives & policies solutions* received a similar level of interest with 23%. *WP3 Testing and development of a toolbox for incentives* received moderate interest with 12%, while *WP6 Coordination & Management* and *WP1 Development of end-users-led soil health business cases framework* received the least interest with only 13% and 2%, respectively.

Figure 2. Which WP is considered more interesting?

Regarding the second question related to the evaluation of the most beneficial results, *New incentives soil health business models* and *Toolbox for incentives* were selected as the most beneficial by almost half of the respondents with 24% and 22%, respectively. This indicates that many of the respondents believe that incentivizing and promoting new business models that prioritize soil health is an effective way to achieve their goals.

Figure 3. Which of the main milestones are more beneficial?

Develop a consolidated CoP and *Business models and Social innovations* received the same percentage of votes at 16%, and were tied for the third most beneficial results. This suggests that creating a community of practice and exploring new business models and social innovations are both seen as important steps in promoting soil health.

Supply Chain Development for Business Models received 9% of the votes, indicating that many respondents feel that prioritizing soil health across the entire supply chain is a key factor in achieving their results.

Highlight benefits obtained from soil health investment and *Roadmap on policies and innovation* both received only 4% of the votes, indicating that they were seen as less beneficial than the other main results.

Finally, both *Soil health business framework* and *Individual policy and innovation lab report* received the lowest percentage of votes at 2%, suggesting that they were seen as the least important result in achieving their objectives.

During the second day of MPE (17/02/2023), it was presented Bulgarian case and the other NOVASOIL case studies (CS). Additionally, it was presented WP 3 approach for inventory and mapping of incentives for improving soil health.

It was organised voting about the most interesting CS using 4 votes per CoP members.

Figure 4. Which case study are more interesting?

The *Soil Fertility Fund* has the highest percentage of 22%, making it the most interesting case study. It is followed by *Organic Wine in Rueda, Spain* and *Crop production – Estonia* both with a percentage of 13% and 12%, respectively. Both *Rabo Carbon Bank* and *Integrated Production in the Vineyards with Winery and Rural Tourism* took 10%.

On the other hand, the three case studies with lowest percentage of about 2% are *District of the Sands*, *A Model for Multifunctional and Sustainable Local Development of Marginal Areas*, and *CO2-Land*.

Questions and comments

During the first MPE there were different discussions related to the presented WPs and the Bulgarian and other NOVASOIL project case studies.

Day 1 – 16/02/2023

During the first day the participants made several discussions and comments.

Wine value chain actors

Milko Yanev agreed that the wineries are the most important in the wine value chain. Especially the big wineries, which produce vine and highly alcoholic beverages. He emphasized that in Bulgaria exist two categories of vineyards

holdings – registered and unregistered. The second category takes a part in almost half of the vineyards in the country and does not receive subsidies. He outlined two groups of vineyards: those with a winery and smaller ones without a winery. These are different types of farms and need a different approach. The unregistered agriculture holdings are difficult to be covered by the policy measures.

Todorka Stoicheva also emphasized on the problem of unregistered farmers. The lack of registration of those vine-growing producers is due to increasing social insurance costs which demotivates them from registration.

Wine tourism

Krasimir Petushanov, the chairman of the Wine-growing cooperative "Brestovitsa" with more than 400 cooperative members, stressed that wine tourism is an important part of the business model. The cooperative uses the cooperative business model to produce and sell wines under the same brand. According to him, 90% of the wineries have the vision to develop a wine tourism business model, and it is not necessary to own a hotel for that purpose. There are many other options to attract tourists. Until now, they work mainly with Plovdiv municipality for wine route development. Also, It is necessary to involve such kind project as NOVASOIL to introduce some novel business models in this direction.

Kiril Minchev stressed that wine tourism is not enough, and thus, only about 4-5% of the production is realized. He understands the role of advertising and emphasized that quality is important.

Todorka Stoycheva stated that some of the large wineries are practicing wine tourism, but some are not interested in wine tourism and are more closed. For them, it is more interesting that wine tourism brings additional publicity and brand recognition. Medium-sized wineries are more interested in wine tourism, and they combine advertising with direct sales.

Different kind of quality schemes – bio wine, PDO and PGI

Kiril Minchev emphasized that the quality of grapes from organic production for winemaking purposes is very low and cannot be compared with conventional production. The presence of certain microorganisms adversely affects the wine. He commented on the use of preparations for the production of wine, emphasizing their important role. He concluded that organic production cannot successfully enter a new market.

Milko Yanev expressed concern that wine could be regulated and labeled like cigarettes, which would negatively affect the market. He expressed the

opinion that small farmers are oppressed and should be supported. He emphasizes the good level of the environment and the quality of the soil. He gave the example that the grape needs fewer treatments here.

Another concern is the categorization of the products. Categorizing is a cumbersome, expensive, and time-consuming process, which leads people to turn to other types of registrations and categorizations.

Dinko Yanev touched on the issue of organic production and that the transition to 30% organic will be hard for the local market. He comments on the organic fertilizers and preparations.

Todorka Stoicheva underlines that the transition from conventional to bio wine production takes between 4 and 6 years. In addition, it takes for PDO 3 years and for PGI it takes less than the previous two. This is the reason why most of the producers are focusing on PGI.

Day 2 – 17/02/2023

The second day of the MPE was focused on the possible business models in Bulgarian CS and methodology for connecting the soil health inventory and mapping of incentives.

The discussion touched on the issue of green cover as a soil conservation practice. The participants united around the conclusion that green cover is not suitable for our climate due to the low amount of precipitation (400-450 ml/sq.m.), and here there are more negatives than positives. Green cover is useful where there is more rainfall, and the wines are grown on a steep slope. The participant concluded that it is necessary to be adopted new policies (green erosion measures) for the regional climate condition.

Maia Miteva from paying agencies offers to use the farm data from Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) to identify the incentives given during the previous planning period (2014-2022). With this approach will be possible to create a map (spatial mapping) for each incentive connected with soil health by EU member state countries based on the real information from the national paying agencies. For example, with incentives – subsidies for the protection of soil erosion in vineyards. All participants in the meeting agreed that such an approach to spatial mapping of applied soil fertility incentives would inform farmers and policy makers about the use of these funds from a territorial perspective. On the other hand, this approach would help the planning process in the next planning period.

List of participants

Table 1 List of participants

Nº	Name	Entity	Sector	Gender
1	Hristina Doicheva	Municipality Agricultural Service, Koprivshitsa	Public administration	F
2	Dimitar Docuzanov	Winery "Rumelia", Panaguriste	Winery	M
3	Marina Mitova	Winery "Manastira", Lesichevo	Winery	F
4	Kiril Minchev	Winery "Starosel"	Winery	M
5	Margarita Gospodinova	Regional Agricultural Advisory Service, Plovdiv	Consulting Services	F
6	Todorka Stoicheva	Executive Wine Agency	Public administration	F
7	Stanislava Panova	Agricultural Credit Cooperative "Solidarnost"	Private sector	F
8	Eli Janakieva	Agricultural Credit Cooperative "Solidarnost"	Private sector	F
9	Ivan Kehaiov	"Solidarnost" 2006 LTD	Consulting Services	M
10	Aneta Valeva	"Solidarnost" 2006 LTD	Consulting Services	F
11	Daniela Dimitrova	"Solidarnost" 2006 LTD	Consulting Services	F
12	Dinko Janev	Experimental Station, Haskovo	Research	M
13	Ivan Gologanov	Agricultural Credit Cooperative "Solidarnost"	Private sector	M
14	Todor Janakiev	Vocational Training Center, Plovdiv	Private sector	M
15	Camelia Tusheva	Vocational Training Center, Plovdiv	Private sector	F
16	Milko Janev	National Association of Bulgarian Wine growers	NGO	M
17	Atanas Tushev	Agricultural producer	Wine grower	M
18	Rusko Panov	"Solidarnost" 2006 LTD	Consulting Services	M
19	Hristina Miteva	Agricultural Credit Cooperative "Solidarnost"	Private sector	F
20	Martin Tushev	Agricultural Credit Cooperative "Solidarnost"	Private sector	M
21	Maia Miteva	Paying Agency, State Fund "Agriculture"	Public administration	F
22	Darina Docheva	Wine-growing cooperative "Brestovitsa"	Wine grower	F
23	Krasimir Patishanov	Wine-growing cooperative "Brestovitsa"	Wine grower	M

Pictures

Denmark

Organising Partner: University of Copenhagen, Denmark

Venue: Online, in Zoom

Time: 20 February 2023, 15:00 – 16:30

Time	Activity
15:00-15:05	- Welcome and introduction (Thomas Lundhede)
15:05-15:30	- Presentation of the project (Thomas Lundhede and Søren Bøye Olsen)
15:30-16:20	- Discussion and feedback from participants
16:20-16:30	- Conclusions and wrap up

Summary of multiplier event:

The event, organized by University of Copenhagen, had nine participants representing University of Copenhagen, the Danish Ministry of Environment, the Danish Climate Council, the Danish Biodiversity council, and the expert group on withdrawal of low-lying soils from agriculture. Relevant stakeholders from several other organisations were also invited (e.g. the Danish Environmental Agency, Aarhus University, the Danish Nature Conservation Association, the Danish Agricultural Agency, The Danish Agriculture and Food Council, and Seges Innovation (private, independent, non-profit agricultural research and development organization), but could unfortunately not participate. This was likely not due to a lack of interest,(many have expressed interest in participating in future Novasoil meetings) but rather due to the meeting taking place in the national winter holiday week.

The event had an overall dual purpose: 1) to inform the stakeholders about the Novasoil project, and 2) to collect their feedback of relevance to the project.

The participants were generally very interested in the Novasoil project and the objectives it is targeting. They highlighted that the project is very timely since there is a lot of current initiatives and interest in relation to soil health, both nationally in Denmark and at the EU level. They did not express a particularly strong interest in any of the case areas, as they were more interested in the Danish context.

Participants expressed an interest in market-based instruments, for instance in relation to carbon farming and carbon credits, but also stressed the importance of not focusing only on a single ecosystem service. While carbon capture and storage in relation to soil health is important in the Danish context, the possible trade-offs between different ecosystem services are important to consider. For instance, while (periodical) flooding of low-lying carbon-rich soils may be beneficial in terms of reducing GHG emissions from said soils, it might lead to reduced retention of phosphorous, which could have adverse effects on surface water quality. It was recommended that the Novasoil project considers to construct a matrix-like mapping of where and how there are positive/negative/no trade-offs between important ecosystem services affected by soil health measures. Such a mapping could serve as a common ground (“a common language”) for the entire project, and it would be beneficial beyond the project.

Another issue raised was the importance of being able to thoroughly measure and precisely quantify effects of soil health initiatives on various ecosystem services. For some ecosystem services this will likely be a challenge, e.g. for biodiversity, so it is maybe better to concentrate efforts on those ecosystem services that are more easily quantified.

In relation to developing successful incentives and business models, the participants recommended both a strong focus on the supply side, in terms of farmers'/landowners' preferences for construction of contracts and agreements, as well as on the demand side, in terms of citizens' preferences and willingness-to-pay for food products related to soil health and for ecosystem services affected by soil health.

Other remarks were, that given the many ongoing policy initiatives at EU and national level directly or indirectly in relation to soil health, the Novasoil project should be prepared to adjust study objectives, policy and research questions, and adapt methods on a short notice, if new policies or initiatives are introduced while the project is ongoing and potentially while data is being collected. It was considered highly likely that there would be new policies and initiatives introduced in this area during the next couple of years.

Finally, the participants expressed that they looked forward to following the Novasoil project and seeing the outcomes.

List of participants

Name	Entity	Sector	Gender
Maria Theresia Hedegaard Konrad	The Ministry of Environment	Public sector	F
Jacob Vesterlund Olsen	Government appointed member of expert group on withdrawal of low-lying soils from agriculture from UCPH	Research & Innovation	M
Niels Strange	Member of the Danish Biodiversity Council representing University of Copenhagen.	Research & Innovation	M
Jette Bredahl Jacobsen	Member of the European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change EU Climate Council and member of the Danish Climate Council, from UCPH	Research & Innovation	F

Gustav Callesen	Secretariat of the Danish Climate Council	Public sector	M
Jesper Schou	Section leader at secretariat of the Danish Climate Council	Public sector	M
Mohammed Alemu	University of Copenhagen	Researcher	M
Thomas Lundhede	University of Copenhagen	Researcher	M
Søren Bøye Olsen	University of Copenhagen	Researcher	M

Screenshots from event:

KØBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET 20/02/2023 10

Vores del af projektet

- Hvordan påvirker fokus på god jordkvalitet offentlige goder
 - Vand, biodiversitet, kulstof, etc?
- Hvordan værdisættes disse af det omgivende samfund?
- Hvordan kan landbruget blive betalt for at levere disse goder?
 - Gennem de skabte produkter?
 - Certificering?
 - Støtteordninger?
- Hvordan kan man få den enkelte landbruger eller jordejer til at indgå frivillige aftaler?
 - Kontraktsmæssige aspekter?

Thomas Lundhede Søren Baye Olsen
Jakob Vesterlund Olsen Gustav Marquard Callesen
Niels Strange Jette Bredahl Jacobsen
Maria Konrad Jesper Sølvér Schou
Mohammed Hussein Alemu

Estonia

Report

Organising Partner: METK

Venue: Online (in Zoom) and in METK (J. Aamisepa 1, Jõgeva alevik, Estonia).
(10 February 2023)

Time: 10:00 – 12:00

Time	Activity
10:00-10:15	- Welcome and introduction (Kalvi Tamm– METK)
10:15-10:45	- Presentation of the project (Kalvi Tamm– METK)
10:45-11:05	- Case studies (Kalvi Tamm – METK)
11:05-11:35	- Questions and discussion
11:45-12:00	- Conclusions and closure

QUESTIONS AND COMMENTS

To steer the direction of discussion next questions were raised:

1. What are the soil health business models in Estonia today and what can be in the future?
2. What are the incentives to estimate soil health by individuals and companies in Estonia?
3. Opinions about soil certification – challenges and opportunities?
4. How the current legislation in Estonia promotes or restricts soil health business?
5. What could be the soil health policy recommendations in Estonia?

The event organized by METK brought together more than 18 participants from different type of entities representing the academic, industrial, farmers and other sectors, with entities such as Ministry of Rural Affairs, Environment Agency, KEVILI (Farmers' cooperative), ETKL (Estonian Farmers Central

Union), EPKK (Estonian Chamber of Agriculture and Commerce) etc. Invitations were sent to 30 persons.

The multiplier event focused on the presentation of the project, introduction of case studies from other partners and on discussion part.

According to the audience, 33% belong to public sector, meanwhile 17 % were farmers and other 50% were researchers.

The project was very interesting for all the participants and they highlighted the need for soil awareness.

There were comments regarding the project:

1. What is a precise definition for “soil health”?
2. Food production is also ecosystem service.
3. This project should support farmers views not only from an environmental point of view. Soil health is very important to farmers as soil is a main tool for plant production.

Comments about the case studies:

1. In Estonia, Information about environmentally friendly agricultural subsidies (managed by ARIB- Agricultural Registers and Information Board) can be connected with a map application.
2. Carbon farming needs more comprehensive measurements and regulations. A lot of questionability.
3. It is emphasized how the farmer can earn through C sequestration. But what happens in a negative scenario? (Obligations, penalties?)
4. How to punish a farmer who emits carbon. For example, manure -> biogas -> C emission. This farmer must buy, not sell C certificates.
5. C farming should be based on the mean value of C_{org} in Europe. Those who are above the average will receive financial support, those who are below must start working for it.
6. If you already have a high C_{org} in the soil, you cannot raise it any further.
7. All kind of soil analyses are important to make future decisions (for example carbon and soil certificates).

General discussion:

1. Main purpose of carbon farming is financial goals not soil health.
2. Assessment of soil health needs qualitative parameters.
3. Important is distinguish: carbon stock, carbon sequestration
4. Soil biota should be valued more.
5. Measurement of carbon content? Depending on the season, environmental conditions, etc. Variability up to 10%.
6. Soil certificates – to determine the value of the land? This is actually a question in design of soil policies. It is plan to regulate soil certification. Certification is not planned to be obligatory, However, if somebody is interested about certification, then the system must be standardised and regulated.

7. The analyses of legislation are in NOVASOIL work plan and the results are promoted to the stakeholders if report is completed. The design of policy recommendations is produced in tight discussion with the representatives of stakeholders.
8. Soil health is supported by paradigm, where agricultural land is rented to the farmers who are using sustainable farm management practises. The land owners and users need an overview about practices supporting soil health.

Venue:

Screenshot about NOVASOIL multiplier event participants in Skype.

Kalvi Tamm introduces NOVASOIL project on NOVASOIL multiplier event. Photo by Merili Toom.

Taavi Võsa (left) moderates the discussion about business models for soil health, on NOVASOIL multiplier event. Photo by Merili Toom.

List of participants

Name	Entity	Sector	Genre
Kalvi Tamm	METK	Researcher	M
Taavi Võsa	METK	Researcher	M
Merili Toom	METK	Researcher	F
Tiina Talve	METK	Researcher	F
Tiina Köster	METK	Researcher	F
Madli Linder	Environment Agency	Public sector	F
Martin Maddison	Environment Agency	Public sector	M
Andres Oopkaup	KEVILI, farmer	Farmer association, Farmer	M
Meelika Sander-Sõrmus	EPKK,	Farmer association	F
Elsa Putku	METK	Researcher	F
Elina Karron	METK	Researcher	F
Priit Penu	METK	Researcher	M
Iiri Raas	METK	Researcher	F
Peep Siim	Environment Agency	Public sector	M

Stella Miil	Environmental Board	Public sector	F
Eike Lepmets	Ministry of Rural Affairs	Public sector	F
Kerli Ats	ETKL (Eestimaa Talupidajate Keskliit)	Farmer association	F
Enn Selgis	Agriculture and Food Board	Public sector	M

France

Report

Aim of the Workshop

The main objective of the Multiplier event titled "The NOVASOIL Project Presentation" was:

- to inform about NOVASOIL research project
- to involve and invite different stakeholders
- to present different project activities that will be developed during the project life cycle

The multiplier event was an opportunity to discuss with the participants and exchange ideas regarding the project and problems related to the soil in the fruit and vegetable sector and to foster the dissemination of the solutions by strengthening collaboration.

The event was addressed to producer organizations, farmers, cooperatives, professional organizations, policymakers, regions, industries, small and medium enterprises, scientific communities and other stakeholders related to the agri-food sector.

Organising Partner: P8 ASSEMBLEE DES REGIONS EUROPEENNES FRUITIERES LEGUMIERES ET HORTICOLES (AREFLH)

Venue: Online Microsoft Teams (session recorded upon participant's agreement)

Time: 3rd February 2023 - 10 am to 12 pm

Prepared by: Eriselda Canaj

Multiplier Event Agenda:

Time	Activity
9:45-10:00	- Connecting participants
10:10- 10:15	- Introduction Speaker -Eriselda Canaj (AREFLH, Bordeaux, France)
10:15-10:45	- Presentation of the project Speaker – Msc. Francisco Jose Blanco Velazquez (EVENOR, Spain, Novasoil Project Coordinator)
10:45-11:00	- Presentation of the Case Studies Speaker -Eriselda Canaj (AREFLH, Bordeaux, France)
11:00-11;30	- Question & Discussion

11:30-11:45	- Evaluation & Feedback
11:45 – 12:00	- Question & answer session

Multiplier Event reporting sheet

Date of the event: 03/02/2023

Responsible partners: AREFLH

Number of Multiplier event Participants: 15 in total

Link of the publication:

<https://www.areflh.org/en/euprojects-ok/novasoil-first-multiplier-event>

<https://novasoil-project.eu/index.php/2023/01/12/the-novasoil-project-presentation/>

N°	Participant Name	
Participants		
1	Berta Baldrich Gonzalez	Delegation of the Government of Catalunya
2	Christian Otol	Bioengineer - Royal Horticultural Society of Gembloux
3	Marie Delion	Fermes des Arches
4	Eloide Champseix	European Landowners Organisations
5	Rosa Jorba	Delegation of the Government of Catalunya
6	Julia Cooper	Organic Research Centre
7	Liga Lips	Institute of Horticultural, LatHort
8	Helene Morat	European Committee of the Regions
9	Suzanne Reynders	INRAE
10	Eloy Suarez Huerta	Hazelnut Company
11	Tahir Basha	SV Veterinary University
Speaker		
12	Francisco Jose Blanco	EVENOR Tech – Project Coordinator
13	Eriselda Canaj	AREFLH
Organisation & support		
14	Laetitia Forget	AREFLH
15	Pauline Panegos	AREFLH
16	Luca Contrino	AREFLH

Presentation delivered by consortium partners:

- **Introduction:** Delivered by Eriselda Canaj (Project officer of AREFLH), lasted about 15 minutes.

The presentation introduces, in the beginning, the association for the participants that didn't know and the introduction and the aim of the NOVASOIL project.

- Presentation of the NOVASOIL project: delivered by MSC Francisco Jose Blanco /EVENOR tech, Seville, Spain, NOVASOIL Project Coordinator) Lasted 15 minutes.

The presentation introduced the NOVASOIL project, the aim, the objective, the work that will be done during the lifetime of the project and the steps forward.

- **Case Studies: Three examples from Europe:** Delivered by Eriselda Canaj (AREFLH, Bordeaux, France, Project officer) last 20 minutes.

The presentation focuses on examples of case studies from across the EU and how that function.

Conclusion of the event:

The Multiplier events were to present to our members/wider networks the NOVASOIL project and as well the case studies that will work during the lifetime of the project.

During the multiplier, the event presented the project the work packages, the next activities and the outcomes of the project.

In addition, the example of case studies has been presented for example:

- the CO2 Land from Germany
- the Integrate Production from Estonia
- the Rabo Carbon Bank from the Netherlands

The aim is to strengthen the participation and to involve different stakeholders during the life of the project to implement together strategies and to be involved in the future in the different surveys to give her opinion. This multiplier event is designed as an opportunity to exchange ideas and problems in the fruit and vegetable sector and to foster the dissemination of solutions by strengthening collaboration. At the same time to provide more information tools for our members to facilitate their work and meet the upcoming challenges in agriculture. In addition to involving different stakeholders in the community of practices to work together to achieve the objective of the project

Key points of the participant's discussion:

Most of the discussion and questions by participants were gathered during the dedicated space at the end of the multiplier event. Clarifications about the case studies that have been presented.

Following the three presentations, participants engaged in open discussion and highlighted the following aspects:

Q: Clarifying the business model of the three cases studied How is paying for these case studies who is the may coming from, and who is the market for this?

A: Most of the case studies are related to the value chain like integrated production the many receive are from industry or market or came from the public administration. Depends on the country for example in Spain the farmers receive a label. Industry pays for this product's high price if you compare it with traditional products. Olive oil in Spain is the main market and integrated production was the bossiness case study with the most of farmers involved. Now we are trying to promote a new business model related to integrated production receive a label. The case studied in the organic wine

the industry pays the farmers to have wine a specific way and provide and provides training support for farmers once a year. The farmers as well can decide if they want to continue with this collaboration with the industry or not. They may come from private and some cases from public administrations.

Q: Rabo Carbon Bank is a log is funded scheme?

A: A bank allocated in the US is a brand that is working in the carbon credit, that is the brand of the business model that is implemented in the wide world. The idea for the collaboration of the Rabo carbon bank is trying to involve them in our pull of the key actor to increase or promote the Rabo carbon bank to invest in soil health not only in the carbon credit. Maybe a payment for the eco-system services or maybe to the value chain but the value chain is more difficult because required involves entities or key actors related to the market of the specific products.

Q: How will evaluate the efficiency of the develop the I business models in terms of carbo fixing?

A: We need to define the effectiveness as the social condition and environmental conditions, the idea is to demonstrate the impact, for instance, the sequestration by comparing at the beginning of the implementation of the business case and during the project. The

investment in soil health needs medium and long term to see the real impact on the soil. The same case studies that we are working on in the project are a long case study "the integrated production" working from 2005 and have a lot of data collected

is easy to demonstrate the impact on soil health. In other cases studied is not possible to demonstrate if they have a positive impact or not. The idea of the multi-disciplinary consortium is to monitor other taps of variables in terms of the job involved, and social perceptions because is very important to implement. Several indicators will be monitoring this project.

II Part Discussion:

Q: Existing different cases studied in other countries?

A: Yes, in the US (promotion of carbon credit) and Australia, and China the market is more complex to develop a business case to prompt soil health.

Q: Can you explain what was meant by the collective implementation of the business model?

A: in this case, the collective implementation is not excluding the other type of business case because the collective implementation required several actors involved in this business case. For instance, 15 farms work in the same line to promote or improve the landscape.

Q: Questions about outcomes during the life of the project the toolbox will be developed for the research for the public administrations to analyse the potential business case or the best way to promote soil health involving the key actors.

Would like to know if this kind of toolbox you are interested or not for daily work?

A: could be nice but that depends on how it will be developed and how it will be looked at, is difficult to predict now. The idea is good because the project is interesting in collecting the existing knowledge not so much introducing the research knowledge but mostly managing and collecting and disseminating them so is very valuable because quite often the researcher obtains data and we are promoting them in research articles, conferences but broader audience is not reached by the communication. The project is good because it promotes existing knowledge.

Q: What kind of future could be involved in this toolbox to be useful for you?

A: the local knowledge will be more valuable, to see more particular regions, particular methods more efficient not only for the carbon sequestration but

also for healing, for farmers only healed is important, at this moment, not all the farmers are understanding these environmental issues of course they know and they are aware of that and they would like to cooperate and to be in the carbon sequestrations.

In conclusion:

The participants have commented that the NOVASOIL project is very interesting. Some of the

participants have expressed an interest to collaborate with another initiative on the soil.

Others have expressed the desire to participate in the Community of Practice.

In addition,

interest was shown regarding the evolution of the project and the next events providing

room for further participation and discussion.

Attachment:

Signature sheet

Venue: Online Microsoft Teams

Name	Surname	Organisation
Berta	Baldrich Gonzalez	Delegation of the Government of Catalunya
Christian	Otoul	Bioengineer - Royal Horticultural Society of Gembloux
Marie	Delion	Fermes des Arches
Eloide	Champseix	European Landowners Organisations
Rosa	Jorba	Delegation of the Government of Catalunya
Julia	Cooper	Organic Research Centre
Liga	Lips	Institute of Horticultural, LatHort
Hélène	Morat	European Committee of the Regions
Suzanne	Reynders	INRAE
Eloy	Suarez Huerta	Hazelnut Company
Tahir	Basha	SV Veterinary University
Francisco	Jose Blanco	EVENOR Tech
Eriselda	Canaj	AREFLH
Laetitia	Forget	AREFLH
Pauline	Panegos	AREFLH
Luca	Contrino	AREFLH

Photo Events:

TS-4 - First Online Multiplier Event - NOVASOIL Project

38:30

EUROPEAN UNION
Funded by the European Union
under grant agreement 101091268

novasoi AREFLH

About AREFLH

- Assembly of European Horticultural Regions (AREFLH) is an association created in 2000, based in Bordeaux (France).
- AREFLH represent the voice of Europe's fruit and vegetable producing regions and their producers organisations in Europe.
- AREFLH is composed of 16 Regions and 37 PO's/APO's in 10 European countries (FR, IT, ES, PT, EL, AT, BE, IR, BL, DE)
- The members of the AREFLH's PO's/APO's represent about 55% of fruit and vegetable production in EU.
- The specificity and strength of the AREFLH lies in its original structure: it is composed of the College of Regions and the College of Producers. The complementarity of the two bodies makes it possible to adapt common positions between the regions and the representatives of the producer's organizations

Eriselda Canaj

Participants: 13

Participants: 14

Ecosystem services

There is a wide variety of ecosystem services but the most used for business models are:

- Carbon Sequestration / Climate Change Mitigation
- Water supply (including those storage and infiltration)
- Erosion and flood control
- Cultural ecosystem services (tourism, cultural or entertainment events)
- More generalists production of food, wood, etc.

Source: Incentives for Ecosystem Services in Agriculture (ES)

Participants: 14

- EC Eriselda Canaj (Organizzatore)
- BG Baldrich Gonzalez, Berta (Esterno)
- C Christian (Invité) (Guest)
- DM DELION Marie (Esterno)
- EC Elodie Champseix... (Guest riunione)
- EH Eloy SUAREZ HUERTA (Esterno)
- FV Fran Blanco Ve... (Evenor) (Esterno)
- JC Julia Cooper (Esterno)

Participants: 15

Final remark!

- We are bulding a CoP around Project objectives across Europe.
- Several topics will be discussed and we will promote the Exchange of knowledge.
- Stay tuned to our social media, Project website and emails from AREFLH and CNRS

Participants: 15

- EC Eriselda Canaj (Organizzatore)
- BG Baldrich Gonzalez, Berta (Esterno)
- C Christian (Invité) (Guest)
- DM DELION Marie (Esterno)
- EC Elodie Champseix... (Guest riunione)
- EH Eloy SUAREZ HUERTA (Esterno)
- FV Fran Blanco Ve... (Evenor) (Esterno)
- JC Julia Cooper (Esterno)

TS.4 - First Online Multiplier Event - NOVASOIL Project

01:14:58

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CO₂ - Land e.V

Local financial capital:

- Non-profit organization
- Sell 80€ - which 55-60€ to give to the farmers
- Sale the certificates

Cost of business model

- Public relation
- Administrative cost
- Modified crop management by participating farmers

Participants: Fran Blanc..., 15

TS.4 - First Online Multiplier Event - NOVASOIL Project

01:16:34

novasoil

Integrated Production

- Climate change – drought, strong winds and excessive precipitations
- Pest attacks – birds, plant diseases, insects, wilds
- Decreases of pollinators - bees and bumblebees
- Lack of good-performance of IT – hardware and grid both, this risk for developers and end-users both
- Economic crisis – high input prices and decrease of agricultural supports.

Enablers:

- Social awareness – consumers are interested in high quality crop seeds, which are more resistant to pests
- Existing farmers network and policies
- Support for agricultural practices, which are good for soil health
- Good IT infrastructure
- Funding of soil research and dissemination/promotion of results
- Dissemination of valuable results from previous soil studies.

Participants: Fran Blanc..., 15

TS.4 - First Online Multiplier Event - NOVASOIL Project

01:26:41

Participants: PP, LF, DM, S, DELION M., Suzanne Dn., LL, MH, Liga Lopez..., Morad HLL., C, EC, Christian D., Eudie Cha., EH, Hoy SUARE., LC

Germany

Report

Organising Partner: LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FÜR
AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG (ZALF), TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT
MÜNCHEN

Venue: Online

Time: February 9, 13:00 - 15:00

Time	Activity
13:00 - 13:05	- Welcome and introduction – organization
13:05 - 13:25	- Introduction – participants
13.25 - 14:00	- Presentation of the project – organization / case studies
14:00 - 14:05	- Break
14:05 - 14:40	- Discussion: key questions
14.40 - 14:45	- Evaluation and feedback, conclusions and wrap up

Participants:

Including the moderators, 20 people participated in the multiplier event. The invited guests were mainly scientists working in the field of soil protection and soil fertility. In addition, there were farmers, policy makers, case study members and other stakeholders.

To get a brief overview, a few general questions about soil health and the participants' relation to it were asked at the beginning. After that, each participant introduced herself or himself and gave a short report about her/his relation to soil and personal expectations about the workshop.

Almost all participants deal directly with soil health in their daily work.

Do you deal with soil health in your daily work?

When asked if the experts feel affected by the state of soil health, 60% answered that they are indirectly affected. 33% feel directly affected and one participant stated that he is not affected.

Are you affected by the health condition of soils?

Almost all participants feel a shared responsibility for improving soil health.

Do you feel you share responsibility for improving soil health?

The expectations of the participants from the Multiplier Workshop were:

- Establishment of a practical network
- Possibility to establish contacts
- Learn about current research work in the field in general and because they work in similar fields.

After this interactive round, the project was presented. The case studies CO2-Land and AgoraNatura were presented by the project leaders themselves. After a short break, the discussion round started.

QUESTIONS AND COMMENTS

To steer the direction of discussion:

1. What are your initial thoughts about the Project?
2. Are you interested by the projects work packages, the expected results?
3. Are there interesting Case Studies consisted with the soil health business typologies in the region?

What are your initial thoughts about the Project?

Initial thoughts about the project expressed by the participants included that the project follows an innovative concept, focuses on a multitude of approaches, and that NOVASOIL addresses the most important issues, in general.

One central question raised at that point was how soil health can be adequately defined. Biodiversity is an important aspect as well as considering the soil biome (and its links to human health that have been discussed recently). It was also mentioned that climate certificates are currently under scrutiny in the public discussion.

Are you interested in the project's work packages and the expected results?

The participants unanimously indicated that they are interested in the project results and work done during the project. This was to be expected considering the participants' professional background.

Are there interesting Case Studies consisted with the soil health business typologies in the region?

The participants mentioned several case studies that are related to NOVASOIL's ideas. These were:

- Bio Boden:

The Bio Boden cooperative buys agricultural land that is for sale. The land is then given to organic farmers or farmed by the cooperative itself according to organic farming practices. One share in the cooperative costs 1000 euros and three shares correspond to an agricultural area of 2000 square meters. (see also [BioBoden Genossenschaft: Unser Weg](#))

- Regionalwert AG:

Citizens can buy a citizen share for an amount of 625 euros or more. The money flows into regional partner businesses in agriculture, regional logistics, gastronomy, consulting and production facilities that meet the initiative's sustainability criteria of operating in an ecological, social and future-oriented manner. (see also [Startseite - Regionalwert AG Freiburg \(regionalwert-ag.de\)](#))

- A.ckerwert

The A.ckerwert project aims to make people aware that land tenants share responsibility for the way their land is managed. By paying a fair rent, they can give the farmer financial leeway to pursue new ways of cultivation that protect both land and nature. The project aims to provide land leasers with assistance in assuming this responsibility. A.ckerwert supports landlords of agricultural land to include sustainability aspects in lease agreements. The project is a platform to bring people together and find solutions that are a win-win for all parties involved: Farmers, landowners and nature. (see also [Ackerwert | Verpachten gemeinsam](#))

- Various initiatives of local water suppliers

Use of self-interest: Initiatives of water suppliers pays premiums ("nitrate premiums") to farmers who leave catch crops standing for a long time to prevent leaching into groundwater.

What do you think are the challenges in developing and implementing soil health business models?

Several key points were discussed during the following discussion. These and thoughts expressed by the participants are summarized below.

- In general, it should be paid attention to **not overburden farmers with regulations.**
- General approach to measuring soil health: **Result-oriented or measure-oriented?**

Participants emphasized the advantages of result-based payment schemes. However, also disadvantages were pointed out, such as the

dependency in farming on external factors (e.g., weather). For example, the influence of dry years make the result-based model vulnerable – and this problem does not improve with current and future climatic changes.

- **Definition of soil health**

Participants agreed that it is necessary to have a clear definition of soil health. It was mentioned that this is also discussed in the context of the EU's Soil Health Law.

The definition of soil health translates into the soil parameters focused on. It was expressed that the view on soil health should not be narrowed down to carbon content. Soil physics might be disregarded in the project to some extent.

- Challenge of **provability and measurement of soil health**

Furthermore, one participant mentioned that a main challenge of the project lies in determining how soil health improvement can be measured. For example, changes in organic carbon contents are reliable only with long time frames and with robust measurement methods that take into account heterogeneity within fields.

Representatives of the CO₂-Land initiative indicated that there are solutions to this concern. In order to measure the improvement in soil health while also capturing heterogeneity as best as possible, only the entire farm is recorded in the CO₂ Land initiative, not individual plots. Mixed samples are taken from 1-3 ha plots to measure the humus build-up. The earliest measurements are conducted 4 years after implementing new practices. By this, the initiative strives for viable proofs at reasonable costs.

- **Fairness**

The question was raised whether farmers who already work in humus conserving ways are disadvantaged if a general increase of the humus content is applied. This is also pronounced given the natural annual fluctuations in humus content. For example, if fixed rates of humus build-up decide over rewards for farmers, this would disregard that regional differences make building up humus more difficult for some farmers than others. Representatives of the CO₂-Land initiative commented that a possible solution consists in mixed remuneration models, which reward both the status quo and improvements in soil health.

- **Regulatory framework**

It was mentioned by one participant that regulatory laws act as barriers for private initiatives and some regulations can act counter-productive. One participant shared her impression that EU policy focuses on regulatory law rather than creating incentives, which contradicts other efforts to foster business models.

- **Appreciation by society**

Private funding can be seen as an opportunity for consumers to show appreciation toward the topic of soil health since consumers in general want their food to be produced sustainably.

Funded by the European Union
under grant agreement N°
101091268

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Vorstellung Projektteam

Leibniz-Zentrum für Agrarlandschaftsforschung (ZALF) e. V., Arbeitsgruppe für Governance von Ökosystemleistungen

Prof. Dr. Bettina Matzdorf
Dr. Cheng Chen
Doktorand: N. N.

Technische Universität München, Lehrstuhl für Produktions- und Ressourcenökonomie

Prof. Dr. Johannes Sauer
Carina Obergröbner
Dr. Fabian Frick

Pictures

Signature sheet

Name	Surname	Organisation	Email	Signature
Fabian	Frick	TUM		
Carina	Obergröbner	TUM		
Cheng	Chen	ZALF		
Katrin	Lück	ZALF		
Martin	Borchert	AgoraNatura		
Margarethe	Reichenspurner	AgoraNatura		
Michael	Schwegler	CO2-Land e.V.		
Paul	Schwegler	CO2-Land e.V.		
Karl	Müller-Sämman	CO2-Land e.V.		
Sebastian	Funk	Syngenta AG		
Thomas	Sixt	TUM (plant sciences)		
Alois	Heißenhuber	TUM / VWU		
Lukas	Bayer	ZALF LUC		
Martin	Wiesmeier	Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft		
Mareike	Söder	Thünen Institut		
Chris	Bamminger	LANUV NRW		
Arne	Hanssen	Schleswig-Holstein State Ministry of Energy Transition, Climate Protection, Environment and Nature		
Kurt	Herbinger	BayWa Group		
Lisa	Fischer			
Cordula	Sonne			

Italy

Report

Organising Partner: UNIFI, UNIFE and IDECO

Venue: Online, in Microsoft Teams. (8 February 2023)

Time: 11:00 – 13:00

Time	Activity
11:00-11:15	- Welcome and introduction and roundtable (Luciana Angelini – UNIFI)
11:15-11:45	- Presentation of the project (Fabio Bartolini– UNIFE)
11:45-12:00	- Question and discussion first round
12:00-12:30	- Case studies presentation (Silvia Tavarini – UNIFI; Daniele Antichi – UNIFI; Gloria Minarelli - IDECO)
12:30-13:35	- Questions and discussion – second round
13:30	- Conclusions and closure

QUESTIONS AND COMMENTS

This section is to note all interesting discussion, comments and feedback received by stakeholders during the event.

This will feed the Report for Deliverable 5.2

To steer the direction of discussion -first round:

1. What are your initial thoughts about the Project?
2. Are you interested by the projects work packages, the expected results?
3. Are there interesting Case Studies consisted with the soil health business typologies in the region?

Second round after case studies presentations

4. What are the forms of incentive that you think are most effective for soil health?
5. What are the main barriers that make the current incentives ineffective?
6. What incentives should be adopted in the future to improve soil health?

The event organized by UNIPI, UNIFE and IDECO brought together about 39 participants, from different sectors.

Figure 1. Participant share and their main sector

The multiplier event was structured as two-ways dialogue between NOVASOIL researchers and other key stakeholders. To pursue such objectives, we plan two rounds of discussions. In the first one we introduced the NOVASOIL project, its objectives, structure and research activities (WPs and planned activities) in order to receive feedbacks from participants. In the second one we delivered the case studies presentation (two from UNIPI and one from UNIFE and IDECO) and we concluded with a discussion on the potential for incentives and other type of economic instruments to pursue soil health objectives. The large participation (37 participants) in the multiplier event shows a very high stakeholder's willingness to be involved in the project activities.

For some participants, there is a lot of interest in the next evolutions in terms of soil policies. In Italy, there is much anticipation for the new CAP Strategic Plan (PSP) 2023-2027, and above all at the EU level after the launching of a soil strategy for 2030, there is interest towards a potential common directive on the soil.

The attendees agree on the saliency and timely of the project considering the relevant contribution of soil health to ecosystem services and the changes in soil health regulation in the coming years. The participants emphasise the need to coordinate efforts to increase the rural actors' willingness to invest in soil health. Some participants declared an interest in the project about

possible organizational solutions, about their effectiveness and implementability. There is also interest in the project's proposed toolkit.

The participants agree on the need to focus better on incentives to facilitate the diffusion of available knowledge and practices in each case study.

“What I perceive as the biggest problem is to find the tools to get farmers to adopt these techniques, because all in all we know them, they could have been a little different, certainly new thing could come out, but what is missing here is to convince farmers to change and therefore the whole part of the project that concerns incentives is very important” [Researcher]

The toolkit (WP3) and coherence analysis (WP4) are the activities that have captured the most attention.

Some converged on the need for analysis about the recovery of what today is considered waste from agricultural processes, and how these new resources can fit with the concept of soil health (e.g. the use of livestock manure to improve soil fertility). Key for several participants will be the role of information and how this should be reorganized in a more capillary way to guide farmers in the transition. For the participants, the objective of an active exchange of knowledge, collaborations, strategies between companies and territorial management subjects is fundamental to improve the overall knowledge of this sector, after all, the soil belongs to everyone.

Pictures from the Meeting

List of participants

	Name	Entity	Sector	Genre
1	Fabio Bartolini	UNIFE	Researcher	Male
2	Silvia Rita Stazi	UNIFE	Researcher	Female
3	Enrica Allevato	UNIFE	Researcher	Female
4	Massimo Coltorti	UNIFE	Researcher	Male
5	Giacomo Ferretti	UNIFE	Researcher	Male
6	Greta Winkler	UNIFE	Researcher	Female
7	Francesco Riccioli	UNIPI	Researcher	Male
8	Roberta Moruzzo	UNIPI	Researcher	Female
9	Luciana G. Angelini	UNIPI	Researcher	Female
10	Silvia Tavarini	UNIPI	Researcher	Female
11	Daniele Antichi	UNIPI	Researcher	Male
12	Daniele Vergamini	UNIPI	Researcher	Male

13	Marco Mazzoncini	Accademia dei Georgofili	Researcher	Male
14	Mario Rosario Rizzi	FLORA srl. Aromatic plants and essential oil organic production	Private sector	Male
15	Sofia Mannelli	Chimica Verde Bionet	NGO	Female
16	Claudia Di Bene	CREA-AA; Soil Hub	Researcher	Female
17	Valentina La Sorella	CREA-PB; EIP soil	Researcher	Female
18	Marco Locatelli	Tuscany Region, Direttore Gestioni Agricole	Public administration	Male
19	Dario Fantechi	Consultant	Service Sector	Male
20	Sara Turchetti	IRPET-Tuscany Region	Researcher	Female
21	Chiara Ferronato	Emila-Romagna Region	Public administration	Female
22	Dania Baldoni	IDECO	Researcher	Female
23	Lorenzo Davino	CREA-AA	Researcher	Male
24	Filippo Zanella	Biokw consultant	Private sector	Male
25	Gino Ghirardello	Farmer	Private sector	Male
26	Maddalena Andreoli	Confcooperative Ferrara	Private sector	Female
27	Carlo Ragazzi	Consorzio degli Uomini di Massenzatica	Private Sector	Male
28	Federica Bigongiali	Fondazione Seminare il Futuro (SIF) Breeding bio	Foundation	Female
29	Mattia Bernardi	Terre dell'Etruria, Società Cooperativa Agricola tra Produttori	Private Sector	Male
30	Gloria Minarelli	IDECO	Researcher	Female
31	Monica Pettirossi	Dondi S.p.A., Farm Machinery Company	Private Sector	Female
32	Andrea de Angeli	Soc. agricola de Angeli	Private Sector	Male
33	Remo Magnani	Pro.Pa.R.	Private Sector	Male
34	Tomaso Bertoli	BioKW	Private Sector	Male
35	Marco Rivaroli	Fondazione per l'agricoltura F.II Navarra	Foundation	Male

36	Martina Berneschi	Consorzio di Bonifica Pianura di Ferrara	Public Administration	Female
37	Francesco Manca	Producer Organisation Ferrara	Private Sector	Male

Latvia

Report

Organising Partner: Union “Farmers Parliament”, Latvia (ZSA)

Venue: Online, Zoom meeting

Time: 26.01.2023. 16.00 – 18.00

Time	Activity
16:00-16:15	- Welcome and introduction (Juris Lazdins, ZSA)
16:15-16:30	- Presentation of the project (Valters Zelcs, ZSA)
16:30-17:10	- Cases studies, Eco-schemes (Valters Zelcs, ZSA)
17:10-17:35	- Questions and discussion
17:35-17:45	- Monitoring indicators for soil health business models (Valters Zelcs, ZSA)
17:45-18:00	- Conclusions and closure

Conclusions and Comments

This section is to note all interesting discussion, comments and feedback receives by stakeholders during the event.

This will feed the Report for Deliverable 5.2

To steer the direction of discussion:

1. We are interested in hearing your thoughts regarding the NOVASOIL project?
2. What are your initial thoughts about the Project?
3. Are you interested by the project work packages, the expected results?

The event organized by ZSA and brought together around 137 participants from different type of institutions, representing the politicians, researchers, advisors, farmers and other stakeholders.

The aim of the multiplier event was introduction of the project aims, objectives and activities, focusing on business cases studies as practical solutions for soil health and make the interest for the stakeholders and relevant parties on the expected project results. The participation of the large number of the participants based on the good advertisement activities due our case study is focused on eco-schemes, which is very actual topic and participants along with the Novasoil project want to know more about the eco-schemes case.

In order to promote the discussion, a roundtable was initiated and a survey was circulated.

Figure 1. Type of entities distribution

According to the audience, 90% belong to farmers community, second largest group are 'other' that citizens - 23%, then follows advisors – 11%, researchers 8.6% and politicians/civil servants – 7,5%.

Novasoil project is very significant for the transfer of knowledge between different regions, countries and research objects.

As the soil is complicated research object, then any kind of knowledge promotes understanding of sustainable usage.

It would be a good contribution during the project if we could explain/explain complex processes in an understandable way/in an interesting language for the end users, it would encourage the involvement of land users/land managers in the process.

Greater emphasis should be given to the microbiological section of the soil, as there are insufficient studies on the biologically diverse environment of the soil, valuable experience.

At the moment, biodiversity, different CO₂ emission separating policies are putting pressure on business and for now there is a big confusion to understand whether it is good or bad for the soil.

According to WPs interests, business cases (WP1) and policies innovation (WP4) were selected as more interesting by the participants.

Related to the **expected project results**, the participants very much expressed interest on successful business cases to promote the soil health in the toolbox.

The participants showed deep interest for the ZSA showcase on eco-schemes with soil friendly agricultural practices. The eco-schemes are very actual topic for the society so the project helps for business development and also providing society awareness.

With the participation in the political discussion the NOVASOIL project results will be bases for justification of the actual situation on the based on the research results.

The campaigns for raising the society awareness on the healthy soil farming practices will be part of the project activities and will be given significant effort.

The second ZSA showcase what type of forest to grow in the certain soil type on the overgrown land would be matter of the discussion in the following meetings.

Zoom Meeting | You are viewing Valters Zelcs' screen | View Options

Funded by the European Union under grant agreement N° 101091268

novasoil ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA

Inovātīvi biznesa modeļi augsnes veselībai INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH (NOVASOIL)

Projekta izplatīšanas seminārs
26.01.2023.
Juris Lazdiņš, Valters Zelcs

Participants (120)

- Zemnieku saeima (Host, me)
- Valters Zelcs (Co-host)
- Juris Lazdiņš (Co-host)
- ATIS Slakteris
- 0012VAKS
- 3
- Agita Dadeka ZS Lejasrēbeni
- Agnese Alpa-Bunke
- Agnese Jēgere z/s 'Lejas Zosēn...
- agro
- Aigars Obukāns
- Aija
- Aija Blūdiņa
- Ainars
- Ainars Juvālis
- AM, S, ZL
- ance
- Anda Kanca
- Andrejs Daudzītis
- Andris Andersons

Uttune Start Video Security Participants Polls Chat Share Screen Pause/Stop Recording Breakout Rooms Reactions Apps Whiteboard End Invite Mute All

Zoom Meeting | Recording...

Autoclean

UK1. Crop production

NL1. Rabo Carbo Bank

GE1. Soil Fertility Fund
GE2. CO2-Land
GE3. AgroNature

ES1. Crop production

LV1. Crop production and animal farming
LV2. Forest management

BE1. Collective governance of Ecosystem Services

ES1. Integrated Production
SP1. Organic wine in Burela
SP3. Laguna Fuente del Rey

IT1. District of the Sands
IT2. Multifunctional and sustainable for marginal areas
IT3. CIRIAA LTR
IT4. Tenuta di Paganico

EU1. Integrated Production in the vineyards

Funded by the European Union under grant agreement N° 101091268

novasoil ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA

Participants (120)

Uttune Start Video Security Participants Polls Chat Share Screen Pause/Stop Recording Breakout Rooms Reactions Apps Whiteboard End Invite Mute All

Digitalizējamies arī mēs!

- <https://app.smartagro.lv/#8/56.964/24.425>
- Zemnieku saeima vairāku gadu garumā ir veidojusi "visa karti"
- Ērts palīgs zemniekiem
- Mērķis – 2023. gada laikā kartē ievietot atsevišķu slāni, kurā būs iespējams apskatīt kuri no laukiem ir pieteikti ekoshēmām.

Netherlands

Report on the Dutch Multiplier Event

Organising Partner: WU

Venue: hybrid (in person at Wageningen University (WU) and online (MS Teams))

Date: 09 February 2023

Time: 9:00 – 12:30

The multiplier event was held together with projects that aim to improve the provision of public goods through contracts. Public goods were considered from a broader perspective than only soil health, to increase the interest and participation of stakeholders. The workshop featured contributions of NOVASOIL, EFFECT, CONSOLE, and contracts 2.0. Discussions with stakeholders were an integral part of the workshop.

The workshop was organized in different modules, each with a specific topic. The agenda of the workshop is presented below. The presentations in the different modules highlighted elements that are important to consider for the design of contracts aiming to promote soil health and carbon farming in particular.

NOVASOIL was introduced at the end of the meeting. The tasks that Wageningen University is leading were discussed in more detail than other aspects of the project because these are most relevant to the participants in the workshop:

- Work package 2, task 2.2: Identification of successful business models (literature review, identification of promising business models)
- Work package 4, task 4.3: Testing of selected policy options, incentive mechanisms (Discrete Choice Experiments)
- The case-study ‘Rabo Carbon Bank’.

Time	Activity
9.00 – 9.15	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Welcome• Introduction• Module 1: What are existing types of contracts for public goods?
9.15 – 9.30	
9.30 – 10.00	
10.00 – 10.30	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Module 2: What do we know about the effectiveness of contracts for public goods?• Coffee break
10.30 – 10.50	
10.50 – 11.20	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Module 3: What can be improved?• Module 4: Upcoming activities – Introducing NOVASOIL
11.20 – 12.00	
12.00-12.30	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Panel discussion and conclusions

QUESTIONS AND COMMENTS RELEVANT FOR THE NOVASOIL PROJECT

This section holds comments and feedback received from stakeholders during the event. These remarks will be considered when designing a Discrete Choice Experiment for the case study in the Netherlands and when developing possible policy innovations (WP 4, task 4.3)

Overall, the project was perceived positively as participants highlighted that farmers need alternative income models that allow them to benefit from public goods (or ecosystem services other than food production).

However, they also highlighted that the current system needs to be changed in order to make these business models successful. Currently, farmers are still focused on improvements of efficiency (higher milking yields per cow / more tons of wheat per hectare), and a less intensive production is often not valued by the market (**highlights the relevance of WP2**).

Especially when determining carbon emissions at the farm level it might be difficult to achieve the extensification that NOVASOIL aims for. This is because if the overall carbon footprint of a farm is determined per kg of produce, this most likely results in intensification rather than extensification. (**policy, therefore, needs to carefully determine where savings are measured (WP4)**).

The stakeholders also highlighted that farmers in agricultural collectives are highly engaged and willing to provide public goods. However, they also displayed doubts about whether society is willing to pay for them. One stakeholder stated 'we are willing to engage now, but if they do not value it (conservation efforts) they should never ask again when we need to stop (when they do not value it)'. Because of the voluntary nature of participation in carbon farming this requires engaged farmers, and the social context and social norms should be included in the analyses (**WP2, WP4**).

An alternative option to private consumers buying credits and agri-environmental schemes that reward the provision of ecosystem services might be to consider new, large buyers (and other alternative contract parties). Contracts with food suppliers were perceived as an interesting option. This applied to already existing contracts between, for instance, dairies that pay producers for implementing biodiversity measures and might also apply for carbon farming (**Rabo Carbon Bank case study**).

Considering the doubts about consumers' willingness-to-pay, policy might be an important additional option to support the implementation of carbon farming. One farmer highlighted that upcoming policies should not only include tightening but also grant non-monetary rewards in the form of relaxation of existing regulations when carbon farming is introduced (**WP4, for instance, if farmers apply more catch crops they are allowed to reduce the distance towards water bodies again**).

Considering project results on contracts and farmers' preferences for contract attributes, it became apparent that farmers highly value flexibility. In terms of agri-environmental schemes, they highlighted that a free choice of measures and the ability to renegotiate contracts regularly are important. Researchers engaged in nature conservation highlighted that for beneficial effects on the environment, long-term commitment seems

essential. This, for instance, applies to permanent pastures where beneficial effects mostly appear in the long run. This most likely also applies to carbon farming, where one could potentially argue that lower levels of farming intensity for one year do not really have an effect and long-term measures are expected to have more impact (**agri-environmental schemes could foster more permanent conservation measures such as agroforestry, grassland conversion, switches towards organic – WP4**).

Considering current agri-environmental schemes, it became apparent that data about their effectiveness are missing (for instance, whether bird conservation is more or less successful in different settings). This most likely also applies to soil conservation measures. For actual decisions on which business models and which policy incentives to promote, the effectiveness will be a crucial point of information (a general observation that relates to different **WPs**).

Type of entities:

Altogether, 17 persons participated in the workshop, 14 participated in person and three joined online. The majority of participants belonged to universities or research organisations. In addition, the workshop was attended by policy advisors; a business developer and representatives of farmer collectives. In contrast to other EU countries, farmers in the Netherlands cannot apply directly for participation in agri-environmental schemes. Dutch farmers are part of agricultural collectives. These collectives organise nature conservation activities in their areas and set up contracts with farmers. Their participation, therefore, allows collecting valuable input on the objectives and farmers' interests.

Venue (Wageningen University):

Workshop (Notes on what is interesting about existing contracts):

Spain

Report

Organising Partner: EVENOR, ASAJA and UPM

Venue: Online, in Google Meet. (10 February 2023)

Time: 10:00 – 12:00

Time	Activity
10:00-10:15	- Welcome and introduction (María Anaya– EVENOR)
10:15-10:45	- Presentation of the project (Francisco José Blanco– EVENOR)
10:45-11:05	- Case studies (José Fernando Robles – ASAJA ; Ana Iglesias – UPM)
11:05-11:35	- Questions and discussion
11:35-11:45	- Monitoring indicators for soil health business models (Francisco José Blanco -EVENOR)
11:45-12:00	- Conclusions and closure

QUESTIONS AND COMMENTS

This section is to note all interesting discussion, comments and feedback received by stakeholders during the event.

This will feed the Report for Deliverable 5.2

To steer the direction of discussion:

7. What are your initial thoughts about the Project?
8. Are you interested by the projects work packages, the expected results?
9. Are there interesting Case Studies consisted with the soil health business typologies in the region?

The event organized by EVENOR, ASAJA and UPM brought together more than 25 participants from different type of entities representing the academic, industrial, farmers and other sectors, with entities such as GMV, SEO-Birdlife, CTA, ULPG, TEPRO, etc.

The multiplier event focused on showing the main project' objectives and provide an overview of WPs and expected outcomes and collect feedback about project perception, but also about interest in case studies and expected results.

In order to promote the discussion, a roundtable was initiated and a survey was circulated.

Figure 1. Type of entities distribution

According to the audience, 40% belong to private sector, meanwhile 20% were farmers and other 20% were researchers.

Regarding project interests and perception, the participants highlighted that the project is ambitious but aligned with SDGS 2030 and European Commission objectives and current challenges for the society and the environment. The project is very interesting for all the participants and highlighted the need of involvement key actors to convince them about the benefits on soil health investment.

About WPs, the most interesting was WP2 and WP4 related to models and policies innovation respectively.

Some expected outcomes were discussed and explained. According to WPs interests, business models (33,33%) and policies innovation (26,7%) were selected as more interesting by the participants.

Finally, the case studies more interesting were those related to carbon credits but in a standardized and certified by third parties. Collective implementation by involvement of key actors is other interested features of business model. These case studies with a positive impact on other ecosystem services were highlighted too and their impact on fauna.

Other remarks received were the potentiality to include additional CS about agricultural lands and cattle raising and the check and monitoring of carbon sequestration rate. On the other hand, the relevance of check environmental and socio-economic benefits was discusses as key message to promote investment. For that, a good communication and dissemination strategy is required to have successful results about investment' promotion.

Venue:

Maria Anaya-Romero está presentando

Modelos de negocio para invertir en salud

Multiplier Event
Horizon Europe, GA 101091268

Dr María Anaya Romero – CEO Evenor-Tech
Equipo de coordinación del proyecto NOVASOIL

Organiza: UPM, ASAJA, Evenor-Tech

Participan: ULPGC, TEPRO, AGQ, UPM, Ecoherencia, INIA, ESRI, SEO, UA, GMV, UNAM, Andanatura, UPO

10:06 | aof-qron-wzd

5°C Soleado

10:06 10/02/2023

meet.google.com/aof-qron-wzd

Ana Iglesias está presentando

Soil functions
Soils deliver ecosystem services that enable life on Earth

<https://www.fao.org/global-soil-partnership/resources/news/detail/en/c/284443/>

11:00 | aof-qron-wzd

Participants: Ana Iglesias, Francisco José Blanco Velázquez, José Fernando ROBLES, Javier Bravo García, 18 más

meet.google.com/aof-qron-wzd

Francisco Jose Blanco Velazquez está presentando

Presentación proyecto NOVASOIL (multiplier event) 10.02.2023

Modelos de negocio para invertir en la salud del suelo

Presentación caso de estudio: **El olivar en producción integrada**

10:44 | aof-qron-wzd

Participants: Francisco José Blanco Velázquez, José Fernando ROBLES, Ana Iglesias, Alba Herrador, 16 más

List of participants

Name	Entity	Sector	Genre
José Fernando Robles	ASAJA-Sevilla	Farmer association	M
Juan José Reche Egea	Farmer	Farmer	M
Manuel Montijano	Asociación de Periodistas de Información Ambiental y AECC Asociación Española de Comunicación Científica.	Researcher – Private sector	M
José Muñoz-Rojas	Universidad de Évora	Researcher	M
Maria del Pino Palacios Diaz	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	Researcher	F
Verónica Asensio	Edafotec	Private sector	F
Jordi Pietx	Consultor externo	Private sector	M
Concepción Mira Rodado	TEPRO, Consultores agrícolas	Private sector	F
Ana Iglesias	UPM	Researcher	F
David Miguel Monge Manso	SEO	NGO	M
Silvia Moreno Mañas	UA	Researcher	F
Julia Yagüe	GMV	Private sector	F

Alba Meijide	Concejalía de Distrito de Ciudad Lineal del Ayuntamiento de Madrid	Public administration	F
Felix González Peñaloza	Evenor-Tech	Private sector	M
María Anaya Romero	Evenor-Tech	Private sector	F
Javier Bravo	Evenor-Tech	Private sector	M
Fernando Alonso	Evenor-Tech	Private sector	M
Francisco José Blanco Velázquez	Evenor-Tech	Private sector	M
Alba Herrador	UPO	Master' Student	F
Jhonny Delva	UPO	Master' Student	M
Carlos Geronimo Salinas	INTA	Researcher	M
Virginia Domínguez	TEPRO	Private sector	F
Ivan Frutos	AGQ	Private sector	M
Nathalie Chravier	CTA	Public administration	F

United Kingdom

Report

Organising Partner: University of Leeds

Venue: Online, in MS Teams. (16th February 2023)

Time: 09:00 – 11:00

Time	Activity
09:00-09:15	- Welcome and introduction (Guy Ziv – University of Leeds)
09:15-09:45	- Presentation of the project (Guy Ziv – University of Leeds)
09:45-10:05	- Case study: Introduction to LENSs (Alan Sargent – 3Keel)
10:05-10:35	- Questions and discussion
10:35-10:45	- Monitoring indicators for soil health business models (Guy Ziv– University of Leeds)
10:45-11:00	- Conclusions and closure

Objective of multiplier event

In line with the NOVASOIL project objectives, the rationale for the University of Leeds multiplier event was to introduce participants to the project, its objectives, the different WPs and expected outcomes. Feedback was collected regarding the project, expected results and the choice of business model case study (LENSs).

In order to promote a discussion, a set of questions were circulated prior to the event. As the audience for this event was limited to those already involved in a Landscape Enterprise Network (LENSs) in the UK, the discussion regarding the NOVASOIL project and the choice of LENSs as a business model case study for promoting soil health was informative.

Participants

The event organized by the University of Leeds brought together nine participants representing stakeholders involved in the Landscape Enterprise Network (LENSs) in the UK. Participants included a sustainability consulting firm (3Keel); members of the business community (Nestlé, Anglian Water, United Utilities, Open Field); and civil society actors (Game and Wildlife Conservation Trust, the Allerton Project, Yorkshire Agricultural Society, Farming and Wildlife Advisory Group South West). Separate MS Teams discussions will be held at a later date with academics who were unable to join the meeting due to university strikes held at national level and other commitments.

Figure 1: Distribution of participants by sector type

Perceptions of NOVASOIL project and choice of business model case study (LENs)

The participants regarded the project as beneficial in terms of enabling them to gain insights into the scope for scaling up LENs in the UK, and were particularly interested in the project objective of building a Community of Practice (COP) around soil health. They welcomed the idea that the project would explore the strengths and weaknesses of the LENs business model, and expressed an interest also in learning about the other NOVASOIL case studies. As indicated in Figure 2, participants were of the opinion that WP2 and WP5 were the most interesting work packages.

Figure 2: Participants' perceptions of NOVASOIL work packages.

Participants regarded the development of a toolbox for scaling up soil health business models as the most interesting, expected project outcome, followed by the development of policy innovations facilitating stacking of payments and a framework outlining how private sector investment in soil health might be complemented by public sector funding for soil-derived ecosystem services.

Participants highlighted the importance of collecting a variety of perspectives on the case study (LENs) and noted a number of challenges to operationalising the business model, from competition for landscape assets to the importance of identifying value-adding business propositions for soil-derived ecosystem service providers (i.e., farmers and land managers) and buyers (i.e., the business community), as well as the key role played by demand- and supply-side aggregators in facilitating trades. Participants stressed the significance of LENs being a demand-led process and being responsive to the needs of the business community, as well the significance of LENs being commerce rather than finance focused, facilitating direct trade related to ecosystem service provision.

Participants described soil health as a 'golden thread' linking stakeholders but mentioned that it was important to recognise other co-benefits and take a multifunctional landscape level perspective on ecosystem service provision. Challenges to operationalising a LENs included the need to attract a sufficient number of ecosystem service buyers and the need to balance having impact at a landscape level (e.g., catchment level) with working at a supply chain level and leveraging associated existing relationships between the business community and farmers/land managers.

Participants expressed an interest in continuing the discussion beyond the multiplier event and committed to sharing additional information if approached by the University of Leeds in the context of follow-up research activities.

Venue: MS Teams

Innovative business for soil health

Multiplier Event
Horizon Europe, GA 101091268

Prof. Guy Ziv – University of Leeds

Participants: 3Keel, Nestlé, Anglian Water, United Utilities, Open field, Game and Wildlife Conservation Trust, the Allerton Project, Yorkshire Agricultural Society, Farming and Wildlife Advisory Group South West

Multiplier event 16-02-23

Main expected outcomes

A toolbox and soil health business models to better design and implement Soil Health Business, built together with a CoP to apply in a real-life context.

It will include:

- A catalogue showcasing existing successful experiences in Europe and outside Europe
- Improved and develop soil health business to be used as models
- A comprehensive guide to the process for the design of Soil Health Business
- Documentation, training and support materials

List of participants

Name	Entity	Sector	Genre
Guy Ziv	University of Leeds	Academic	M
Lisette Phelan	University of Leeds	Academic	F
Alan Sargent	3Keel	Sustainability Consulting Firm	M
Matthew Ryan	Nestlé	Private sector	M
Richard Jenner	Open Field	Private sector	M
James Airton	United Utilities PLC.	Private sector	M
Richard Reynolds	Anglian Water	Private sector	M
Chris Hewis	Anglian Water	Private sector	M
Alice Midmer	Game and Wildlife Conservation Trust	Civil society actor	F
Jenny Phelps	Farming and Wildlife Advisory Group South West	Civil society actor	F
Ben Barnett	Yorkshire Agricultural Society	Civil society actor	M

Guideline

NOVASOIL

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

Grant agreement ID: 101091268

Guidelines for Multiplier Events

Project	NOVASOIL
Project title	INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH
Work Package	5
Deliverable	5.2 Report on first round of multiplier events
Period covered	M1-M4
Publication date	
Dissemination level	
Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this report	EVENOR
Authors	
Contributors	

Summary

The current document is focused to support in the development of multiplier events. At the end, a report template can be found.

Guideline

Multiplier Events

The goal of a multiplier event is to strengthen the links and involvement of key stakeholders, to implement strategies for information flow and co-working, as well as supporting successful surveys and questionnaires, and to launch invitations for further participation in project activities. It is important to reach people outside the Consortium.

During the project life time, Partners will organize two Multiplier Events in their country:

1. At the beginning of the project to engage stakeholders
2. At the end of the project to disseminate project results

Partners involved: ALL

Each partner will be responsible for organizing a Multiplier Event, and inviting relevant actors and stakeholders (5-10), in collaboration with relevant partners. This task is due before mid-February 2023

The aim is to attract attention and receive input from participants.

It should take the form of a workshop (2/3 hours) and should describe the overall project to potential stakeholders (policy makers, local government and public procurement authorities, private stakeholders, such as companies, industry, interested in Project results, ICT industry from big ICT players to SMEs providing hardware and software solutions including AI, research community such as universities and scientific institutes, standardization bodies and relevant harmonization organisms, multi-stakeholder networks or initiatives, NGO, general public, etc)

Within this document you will find:

- Template Agenda; to be filled out by the organising partner
- Signature Sheet; to be signed by participants
- Summary of discussion, comments and questions; to be filled in by organising partner

All documents should be filled in and sent back to EVENOR: m.anaya@evenor-tech.com / f.gonzalez@evenor-tech.com / fj.blanco@evenor-tech.com

This document will feed into to the overall report which will be Deliverable 5.2
(Report on first round of multiplier events.)

Report

Organising Partner:

Venue:

Time:

Time	Activity
xx-xx	- Registration
xx-xx	- Welcome and introduction – organization
xx-xx	- Presentation of the project – organization
xx-xx	- Discussion: Key Questions
xx-xx	- Evaluation and Feedback
xx-xx	- Conclusions and wrap up

QUESTIONS AND COMMENTS

This section is to note all interesting discussion, comments and feedback received by stakeholders during the event.

This will feed the Report for Deliverable 5.2

To steer the direction of discussion:

10. What are your initial thoughts about the Project?
11. Are you interested by the projects work packages, the expected results?
12. Are there interesting Case Studies consisted with the soil health business typologies in the region?

